

IMPULSE

IMmersive digitisation: uPcycling cULTural heritage towards new reviving StratEgies

Deliverable 5.3

Setting-up the digital
co-working space

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2 Executive summary

The Deliverable D5.3 provides the information about the process and the implementation of the collaborative space that will be adopted by IMPULSE partners and the IMPULSE Community of Practice along the duration of the project and during specific initiatives. The document introduces the main Objectives of the collaborative space, defining the scope and target audiences that will be supported with specific functionality according to three channels of action (Education: Teaching & Learning, Creation: Artistic Research, Connection: Creative Industries) connected to the development of future-oriented prototypes. Furthermore, the document explains how the collaborative space will support the hybrid setting in which the IMCo activities will take place: it is a digital working space, already presented in the D5.2 and it will help to monitor the participation of the IMCo throughout the duration of the project.

Key words:

Digital co-working space, hybrid community, co-creation, customization.

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4 Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
CCI	Cultural and Creative Sectors and Industries
DX.X	Deliverable number X belonging to WP X
EC	European Commission
GX	Group X
WP	Work Package
IMCo	IMPULSE Community of Practice

5 Introduction

The collaborative space foreseen for the IMCo is an open and easy-to-use digital working space, allowing synchronous and asynchronous text chat, resource sharing via hyperlinks and uploaded files (text and multimedia files), and integrating functionality for video and voice conferencing.

As described in the project proposal, Mastodon would have been the platform of choice to build the digital collaborative space. However, after further research carried out by UNIBO consulting the NKUA and JU management Team, Discord has been identified as the most suitable platform to host the IMCo digital workspace as it presents built-in features that enable collaboration between its Users. Mastodon might be possibly adopted in the near future as a tool that serves the purposes of disseminating IMPULSE events and results and promoting engagement and participation to the IMCo.

The idea is to organise the IMCo's dedicated server on Discord in a general channel – a space dedicated to getting to know each other and connect by interests - along with specific multiple channels dedicated to the three focus areas (**Education**: Teaching & Learning; **Creation**: Artistic Research; **Connection**: Tech-Creative Industries). The server will work as a place to meet, collaborate, and share ideas, offering different engagement possibilities, e.g. news only, prototypes feedback, connection, and exchange).

The digital working space is set-up by UNIBO with the help of NKUA and administrated/moderated by IMPULSE Partners. The Community Members when accessing the digital platform will have to adhere to community guidelines – included in a dedicated channel - to ensure that no misconduct occurs within the platform. The Community guidelines will ensure meaningful and respectful interactions between the Community Members.

5.1 Objectives of the digital co-working space

The digital co-working space supports the IMPULSE project by fostering collaboration, feedback, and innovation among its diverse community. The key objectives are:

1. **Fostering knowledge sharing and co-creation** by enabling peer-to-peer learning across disciplines. By bringing together academia (researchers, professors, students), cultural heritage institutions, artists, and practitioners from the creative industries, the space allows for contributions from each perspective, encouraging the exchange of ideas and best practices.
2. **Supporting IMPULSE's pilot-prototype development.** The digital co-working space will provide a platform to gather continuous feedback on the IMPULSE project's prototypes throughout their development. Members of the community, including researchers, students, artists, and cultural heritage practitioners,

will engage with the prototypes at various stages, offering insights and suggestions that will help refine and improve these tools before they are finalized.

Such feedback loop is valuable as it might contribute to inform prototypes with real-world needs expressed by the target audience. The feedback loop might also contribute to informing prototype development with best practices in the field.

3. **Promoting interdisciplinary collaboration**, which is central to the IMPULSE project's approach to digitised cultural heritage. The digital co-working space will provide an environment where Members from different sectors—academia, cultural heritage institutions, creative industries—can discuss common challenges and exchange practical insights.
4. **Ensuring accessibility and participation** to pilots stemming from a European-scaled project. The flexibility of the digital environment allows participation and inclusion of Members worldwide offers flexible, digital participation for a global audience, allowing members to engage synchronously or asynchronously.
5. **Establishing a community to keep the conversation going.** Establish a lasting network of professionals working on digitized cultural heritage coming from different areas - education, business, innovation - to facilitate continued collaboration beyond the project's duration.

6 About the platform: why Discord for IMCo

6.1 Premise: Mastodon replacement

As by the project proposal, Mastodon would have been the platform of choice to build the digital collaborative space. However, after further research carried out by UNIBO consulting NKUA and JU management Team, Discord has been identified as the most suitable platform to host the IMCo digital workspace as it presents built-in features that enable collaboration between its Users. Mastodon will be kept as a tool useful to disseminate IMPULSE events and results and to promote engagement. Discord has been established as a popular platform for communication and collaboration, especially among digital communities. To a Community of Practice (D5.2), Discord offers a unique variety of features that support collaboration, knowledge sharing, and sustained engagement.

6.2 DISCORD Co-working space

Below are some of the key benefits of using Discord as the platform of choice for a digital co-working space for the IMPULSE Community of Practice (IMCo):

- **Real-time collaboration and communication**

Discord allows for seamless, real-time interaction through text, voice, and video channels. Particularly, as for voice channels, Discord allows visualising who is in the room. Additionally, it is easy to switch from one room to another by just switching channels. Discord also allows videocalls, with the possibility to share the screen and streaming content. This instant communication is essential for communities of practice, as it fosters rapid knowledge sharing and feedback. The ability to engage in live conversations, host voice meetings, or share screens during co-working sessions encourages dynamic collaboration, making it easier for members to work together on tasks, brainstorm ideas, and solve problems in real time.

- **Customizable channels for structured discussions**

A significant advantage of Discord is its channel-based structure. Communities can create specific text and voice channels dedicated to different topics or areas of practice. This allows Members to navigate and eventually organise discussions by themes, special interests, or project phases, avoiding cluttered communication. The possibility to create dedicated channels for specific topics and scopes – including and not limited to announcements, forums, threads, event calendars, and live stages - or even subgroups within the community, invites participants to navigate and contribute to relevant discussions.

- **Content sharing and archiving**

Discord supports various types of content sharing, including documents, multimedia, and links, which makes it easy for Members to share resources and collaborate on projects. All messages and shared content are archived in the channels, so Members can go back and reference previous discussions, files, or important announcements. This feature allows the community to build a knowledge repository over time, serving as a valuable resource for both new and long-standing members. Discord's upload limit for files is 25 MB per file. However, users can share larger content by linking to external repositories, allowing them to share material efficiently while keeping file sizes manageable.

- **Community-building through engagement**

Discord encourages both synchronous and asynchronous engagement. Members can join live discussions, co-working sessions, or take part in ongoing conversations by catching up on messages left in their absence.

- **Fosters a Sense of Belonging**

By bringing together individuals with shared interests or goals, Discord fosters a strong sense of community and belonging. Features like voice channels, general chat areas, and even community events create opportunities for members to bond, network, and support one another.

- **Roles and permissions for easy community management**

Discord offers a robust role and permission system that allows community leaders to easily manage large groups of people. Admins can create custom roles (e.g., moderators, mentors, general members) and assign permissions, ensuring that only specific Members have access to managing channels or administrative functions. This is critical for maintaining order in large communities of practice and ensuring that communication and activities remain on track. Additionally, roles in Discord can overlap, meaning that users can be assigned more than one role simultaneously, which adds flexibility to how permissions are managed. Roles can also be easily and automatically assigned by bots, making the process more user-friendly for admins. A channel dedicated to roles will guide members through the available roles, clarifying the features and permissions associated with each one. This ensures that Members understand their responsibilities and access levels, contributing to a well-organized and smoothly functioning community.

- **Integration of bots for enhanced features**

One of Discord's most powerful features is the ability to integrate bots to automate tasks and enhance the community experience. Bots can perform a variety of functions, such as sending reminders for events, facilitating polls, assigning roles, or even helping with notetaking and project management. This helps the community streamline its workflow, manage co-working sessions efficiently, and stay organized without manual effort.

- **Cross-platform accessibility**

Discord is available for various devices/OS. This cross-platform accessibility ensures that Members of the community can participate from anywhere, using any device. Whether they're at home, in the office, or on the go, Members can stay connected to the community, access important discussions, and contribute to ongoing collaborations.

- **Affordable and scalable solution**

Discord is free to use, which makes it an affordable option for communities of all sizes. Whether the community consists of a small group of practitioners or a larger, global network, Discord's model ensures that even the most basic features (which are extensive) are accessible without financial strain.

- **Privacy and security features**

Discord offers secure, private servers, meaning that only invited members can access the community. This ensures that discussions, knowledge sharing, and co-working activities occur in a controlled environment. Additionally, the platform has built-in moderation tools to help administrators maintain a safe and welcoming space, including automated spam filters, the ability to mute or ban users, and options for reporting misconduct. Furthermore, specific bots can significantly enhance server security and management. Bots can improve security in different ways:

- **Moderation bots:** Bots like MEE6 and Dyno are popular moderation tools that automatically detect rule violations such as spam, offensive language, or inappropriate content. These bots can automatically mute or ban users based on set criteria, providing a consistent and automated layer of moderation.
- **Safety bots:** Bots like SafetyAtLast and Beemo monitor for potential threats and behaviors such as harassment or malicious links. They can automatically warn or kick users who violate safety guidelines. This proactive monitoring helps reduce the workload for human moderators by automating routine security tasks.
- **Security bots:** Bots like Wick or SecurityBot specialize in handling potential server raids or malicious actors by preventing mass invites, detecting suspicious account behavior, and restricting permissions until new users are verified. These bots ensure that only legitimate Members can engage with the server.
- **Christine (for specialized moderation):** The Christine bot is a more focused tool, designed to monitor for and respond to sensitive behaviors, such as sexual harassment, toxicity, or signs of depression. It can send alerts to moderators and even provide support resources, ensuring that communities remain both safe and supportive environments for all Members.

By utilizing these bots, server admins can automate much of the work involved in managing large communities, from detecting harmful behaviour to enforcing rules, making the server more secure and less burdensome to moderate.

7 Setting-up the digital co-working space

In the following section, the document will outline the key steps in setting up the digital co-working space on Discord. It will begin by **defining the objectives of the co-working space**, clarifying its purpose and expected outcomes within the Community of Practice. Next, it will focus on **identifying the target audience**, ensuring the co-working space is tailored to meet the needs of the Members of the Community of Practice. Finally, it will provide guidance on **designing the structure of the co-working space**, covering the setup of channels, the creation of roles, and the configuration of permissions to ensure smooth collaboration and effective management.

7.1 Target audience

The target audience, as outlined in **D29**, is specifically tied to the three main pilots of the project: **Education (Teaching & Learning)**, **Artistic Research (Creation)**, and **Creative-Tech Industries (Connection)**, ensuring a broad, interdisciplinary engagement.

In this sense, target audience covers the following areas:

- **Artists and Designers:** by providing a platform for showcasing their work, especially those exploring digital art, game design, and interactive installations, artists will gain visibility and opportunities to engage with new audiences.
- **Cultural and Art Institutions:** museums, galleries, and cultural organizations will benefit from the exhibition's innovative approach to blending digital and historical narratives, potentially attracting broader and younger audiences.
- **Local Communities and the General Public:** visitors will be exposed to thought-provoking, interactive experiences that challenge traditional perspectives on history, technology, and art, enriching their cultural knowledge and engagement.
- **Academics, researchers and students:** those studying digital culture, participatory art, or the intersection of technology and history will find valuable material for their work, opening up avenues for further research and collaboration. Moreover, for academics, specially design teachers, who are doubtful about virtual worlds potentialities for creation and didactics, this collaborative space will provide a terrain for lively discovering and familiarizing with this kind of environment and human practices pertaining to it.
- **The Digital and Gaming Industry:** the exhibition will highlight the potential for video games and digital spaces as artistic mediums, encouraging cross-industry collaboration and promoting the creative potential of these technologies in cultural contexts.
- **People from similar EU projects:** to avoid duplication but to also find partners for future projects.

7.2 Intended uses of the digital co-working space

The digital co-working space on Discord is designed to facilitate collaboration and engagement throughout the various stages of the IMPULSE project. Its intended uses span across key events and intervals, ensuring continuous interaction among community members. The primary uses are:

- **During Pre-Hackathon Workshops:** the digital space will serve as a central hub for communication and preparation before and during the three Pre-Hackathon workshops. Participants can use it to exchange ideas, provide feedback, and collaborate on the prototypes, both synchronously and asynchronously. Discord will allow partners to collect engagement data about the IMCo and about the effectiveness of the IMPULSE prototypes.
- **In-between Pre-Hackathon Workshops:** between the Pre-Hackathon events, the space will remain active for ongoing discussions, refinement of ideas, and coordination. This will ensure that momentum is maintained and that participants can continue working on tasks, share updates, and stay connected with one another. It will be used also to increase the exchange of information/knowledge about events, initiatives connected to IMPULSE topics.
- **For the final Hackathon Event:** during the Final Hackathon, the platform will play a critical role in hosting real-time collaboration, project tracking, and coordination. Members will be able to participate in live discussions, engage in collaborative activities, and provide feedback on final prototype developments.
- **For the Final Meeting:** in preparation for and during the Final Meeting, the co-working space will be used for organizing sessions, managing logistics, and enabling participants to share their final insights and contributions. It will also be a space to reflect on the outcomes of the project and ensure that any final materials are shared with the broader community.

The digital co-working space offers a tool to support the organisation and delivery of upcoming workshop events in different ways. In fact, while designing and organising which activities will be **in presence-only**, **digital-only**, or **hybrid** is a crucial aspect to maximize the value that the digital co-working space might bring in. This decision directly impacts the accessibility, participation, and engagement of the community during these events.

- **In presence-only activities:** these activities are typically hands-on or location-specific, requiring physical attendance. It is important to identify and organise such events for tasks that benefit most from direct interaction, such as physical prototype demonstrations or local networking events. In these cases, communication in the digital co-working space can still support participants with preparation and post-event discussions.
- **Digital-only activities:** conducted entirely online and facilitated through Discord, these activities are ideal for global participation and tasks that don't require physical presence, such as virtual brainstorming, asynchronous discussions,

and digital presentations. Text, voice, and stage channels ensure smooth management and interaction. External links to demos and prototypes can be embedded directly in Discord, allowing participants to experience them and provide feedback within the platform.

- **Hybrid activities:** for activities that can be effectively conducted in both physical and digital spaces, hybrid formats offer the best of both worlds. These activities require coordination between in-person and digital facilitators to ensure that both groups of participants are equally engaged. Discord will serve as the platform for the digital side of hybrid events, with stage channels for live streaming and text-based channels for real-time feedback. Discord can also assist in the coordination of in person and hybrid events. It can help with real time polls, voting, sharing presentations slides and notes for each session. Facilitators on both ends—physical and digital—will work together to ensure seamless integration, allowing participants in both spaces to interact, collaborate, and contribute in real time. Here, external links to demos and prototypes can be embedded directly in Discord, allowing participants to experience them and provide insights back within the platform.

Careful selection of which format to use for each activity ensures that the workshops and events are accessible to all members, fostering a multi-layered experience for them. Moreover, these efforts aim at ensuring inclusive engagement regardless of geographic location.

7.3 Designing the digital co-working space

The digital co-working space is designed to facilitate seamless collaboration and communication among the community Members. The following section digs deeper into the structure of the digital co-working space, highlighting channels and presenting their purpose and sub-structure.

7.3.1 General information on the digital co-working space

Server name: IMPULSE | Community of Practice

Server invitation link: <https://discord.gg/UfEgM8B>

Status: enclosed beta (WP5 team). Launch and test scheduled in October 2024.

Roadmap:

[Aug-Sept 2024]	Setting channels & environment
[Mid Oct 2024]	Run environment test with C&D Team (all representatives)
[Late Oct 2024]	Open environment to IMPULSE partners & IMCo subscribers

7.3.2 Categories and channels

Figure 1. Screenshot of the homepage of the digital co-working space.

The digital co-working space on Discord is structured as illustrated in **Figure 1**. This layout includes dedicated channels for community rules and moderator-only discussions, along with sections for general information about the IMPULSE Community of Practice (IMCo) and the IMPULSE project. Key channels such as "**announcements-and-calls**" and "**event-agenda**" are designed to keep the community updated on important events and project activities.

Furthermore, the workspace is divided into sections for each of the three main project prototypes—**Education**, **Creation**, and **Connection**—allowing focused discussions and collaboration within specific domains.

Figure 2. Screenshot displaying the house-rules channel in the “Community Info” category.

The category “**Community Info**” is the very first category that Members encounter when visiting the digital co-working space. It is made of two channels:

- **#house-rules** (Figure 2) contains the community guidelines and rules Members must follow. New Members will be automatically directed to this channel to review the community guidelines.
- **#moderators-only** is a private channel for moderators to manage community-related tasks.

The category “**Welcome to IMCo**” is designed to orient new Members and provide essential information about the IMCo. It includes several key channels:

- **#about-imco**: offers an introduction to IMCo, explaining its purpose, goals, and the benefits of joining the community.
- **#announcements-and-calls**: a space for important updates, announcements, and open calls related to the project. Only moderators are assigned the rights

of posting in this channel. However, Members can contact moderators and suggest events to be shared with the community. Particularly, this channel can be used to broadcast events about:

- **Project announcements:** key developments within the IMPULSE project, including milestones reached, updates on ongoing activities, or significant news.
- **Open calls:** invitations for community Members to participate in events, workshops, hackathons, or feedback sessions related to the project's prototypes. Calls may also extend to more general events, but still resonant with IMPULSE's themes, providing additional opportunities for engagement and collaboration within the broader context of cultural heritage digitisation and creative industries.
- **Updates and deadlines:** notifications about upcoming submission deadlines, and other time-sensitive information, allowing Members to stay informed and plan their participation accordingly.
- **#event-agenda:** the channel displays details on upcoming events, workshops, and other scheduled activities within the community.

Figure 3.1. Screenshot of the #event-agenda channel.

Figure 3.2. The "Add to calendar" option available in the #event-agenda channel.

The **#event-agenda** channel not only provides detailed information on upcoming events but also includes a convenient **"Add to Calendar"** feature (Figure 3.2). This allows Members to seamlessly add events to their preferred calendar platforms, such as Google Calendar, Yahoo, or Outlook, or download an ICS file for manual import. This integration ensures that participants can easily schedule and keep track of important community activities.

- **#about-the-project:** provides a comprehensive overview of the IMPULSE project, ensuring that all Members are informed about the project's objectives and scope.

"The Plaza" is the category working as a central hub for community interaction and casual engagement. This category helps create a sense of community, fostering both professional and informal interactions, which is key to maintaining an active and engaged digital co-working space. It includes the following channels:

- **#general:** A space for open, project-related conversations where Members can discuss various topics, ask questions, and share ideas.
- **#introduce-yourself:** a welcoming channel for new Members to introduce themselves, share their background, and become acquainted with the community.
- **#impulse-manifesto:** this channel has been set-up as part of an internal initiative involving **WP5**, with a focus on engaging the entire project's work packages (WPs). This channel is dedicated to collaboratively shaping the vision and guiding principles of the IMPULSE project. As IMPULSE taps into creativity to explore new perspectives and meanings through the design of experiences *with* and *for* digitised cultural heritage, the manifesto embodies the community's collective aspirations in such a direction.

As such, the manifesto is more likely to be **co-designed** with input from the IMCo. It invites Members to contribute their ideas, inspirations, and visions on how digital cultural heritage can evolve through creativity. This participatory approach ensures that the manifesto reflects a diverse range of perspectives and fosters innovation, aligning with the project's goal of creating immersive, user-centered experiences. Through this channel, the community becomes an active part of the project's narrative, contributing to its evolving identity and shared mission.

- **#off-topic:** a casual space for non-project-related conversations, allowing community Members to engage on different levels and build relationships. A document sharing server will be further implemented to better support content sharing and uploading.

The “**Repository**” is a dedicated category designed to house essential resources and materials for the community. It serves as a central repository for documents, links, and other important content relevant to the IMPULSE project. The key channel under this category is:

- **#imco-resources-and-links:** this channel is used to share and store valuable resources, such as documents, reports, research papers, and external links that are pertinent to the community's activities and goals. It acts as a reference hub where members can easily access the materials needed for ongoing discussions, project work, and collaboration.

The following categories “Education Prototype”, “Creation Prototype” and “Connection Prototype” are specifically designed to organize and focus discussions, resources, and activities related to the three main pilots of the IMPULSE project, as detailed in **D29**.

- **Education Prototype:** Aligned with the **Teaching & Learning** pilot described in D29, this category facilitates discussions on immersive educational practices and the integration of digitized cultural heritage into modern educational frameworks. It provides channels for feedback and collaboration on prototypes related to educational content and methods.

- **Creation Prototype:** tied to the **Artistic Research** pilot referenced in D29, this category focuses on the artistic re-interpretation and speculative reframing of digitized cultural assets. It offers a space for artists, researchers, and practitioners to explore and collaborate on how digital heritage can inspire new forms of artistic expression, as outlined in the IMPULSE project's goals.
- **Connection Prototype:** corresponding to the **Creative Industries** pilot in D29, this category is dedicated to discussions on digital asset integration, platform interoperability, and the broader connection of cultural heritage to creative industries. It focuses on how IMPULSE's prototypes can facilitate new collaborations between digital heritage and creative industries.

These categories have been designed to support the hybrid workshop events that will be organized to launch each prototype and engage the audience, as outlined in **D29**. To facilitate this, each category includes both **text-based and voice-based channels** (Figure 4), allowing for flexible, real-time discussions and collaboration. Additionally, **Stage channels** are available for broadcasting live plenary sessions, making it easy to host large group events and presentations.

An additional feature that might be adopted in these categories is the **Forum channel**, a structured space designed for more in-depth, asynchronous discussions. The Forum channel would allow members to post topics and receive threaded responses, making it ideal for ongoing debates, detailed feedback, or brainstorming sessions that can continue beyond live events. This would provide another layer of engagement, fostering both real-time and ongoing interaction within the community.

*Based on the activities that are planned to be delivered in **presence-only, hybrid mode**, or **digital-only** (via Discord), each workshop organizing institution can **customize the category** to fit the specific needs of their event. For instance, institutions can decide which channels to emphasize or create, such as prioritizing **Stage channels** for live streaming during hybrid workshops or using **text-based channels** for digital-only discussions and collaboration.*

*Customizations could include adding channels for in-person events, such as logistical discussions or venue-specific information, or enabling **Forum channels** for asynchronous discussions where attendees can engage before, during, or after the event. This flexibility allows each institution to tailor the co-working space to effectively support their specific workshop activities, ensuring a seamless experience regardless of the mode of delivery.*

Figure 4. Screenshot displaying the sub-structure of the “**Education Prototype**” category, which serves as a template applied to each of the prototypes (Education, Creation, and Connection).

7.3.3 Roles and permissions

The **Roles** feature in the digital co-working space allows for the effective organization and management of community members by assigning specific permissions and access levels.

Figure 5. Screenshot displaying the roles of the IMCo.

The roles include:

- Admin:** This role grants full administrative privileges to manage server settings, channels, and moderation activities. It is typically assigned to the Core Team responsible for overseeing the server's operation. This role is restricted to Project Coordinator and WP5 Leaders (UNIBO).
- IMPULSE Core Partner:** Members with this role are members of the IMPULSE project's core partnership. **They are assigned moderating permissions**, including broader access to various channels and more input in decision-making processes.
- Education Prototype Expert:** this role is designated for experts actively involved in the **Education Prototype**, both during and after the hybrid event. These Members will guide and inspire the digital audience with their expertise, contributing to discussions on immersive educational practices. Additionally, they will facilitate sessions in the digital space, ensuring productive engagement and knowledge sharing within the community.

- **Creation Prototype Expert:** Just like the Education Prototype Expert, this role is designated for experts involved in the **Creation Prototype**, during and after the related hybrid event. These Members will guide the digital audience, offering their expertise in artistic research and digital heritage creation. They will facilitate discussions and sessions in the digital space and act as the **primary contacts of reference** for any inquiries or activities related to the Creation Prototype.
- **Connection Prototype Expert:** Members with this role engage in the **Connection Prototype**, focusing on bridging cultural heritage and creative industries. Similar to the previous “Expert” roles, Connection Prototype Experts will support and facilitate digital activities and interactions in matters connected to the pilot.
- **IMCo Member:** This role is for general Members of the IMPULSE Community of Practice (IMCo), granting them standard access to participate in discussions and activities. Since Discord allows multiple roles per member, IMCo Member can be seen as an introductory role, that may be paired with additional roles to customize one’s own profile.

These roles help ensure a structured environment where Members can collaborate efficiently based on their area of expertise and involvement within the project.

Additional labels can be designed along the way to ensure a more customizable profile for each Member and smoothen the networking and matchmaking within the digital co-working space. Examples of labels may look like the following:

- **Expertise-wise:** student, professor, researcher, facilitator, tutor, practitioner, manager, enthusiast.
- **Country-wise:** Greece, Germany, France, Italy, Malta, Poland, Spain, etc.
- **Affiliation (Organisation / partner institution):** this will facilitate people who want to reach out or have a specific question.

7.3.4 Moderation processes and tools

The server’s moderation framework is overseen by **Admins** and **IMPULSE Core Partners**, who ensure that all interactions and content shared within the digital co-working space adhere to the community guidelines and ethical standards. These measures are crucial for maintaining a safe-for-work (SFW) environment that is respectful, inclusive, and aligned with research ethics.

Key aspects of the moderation process include:

- **Oversight by Admins and IMPULSE Core Partners (moderators):** administrators and designated core Members are responsible for monitoring content, resolving disputes, and ensuring that the community's code of conduct is respected. They actively intervene if inappropriate content or behavior arises, ensuring that the space remains professional and conducive to productive collaboration.
- **Content moderation:** all content shared within the channels is subject to review to ensure it is research-focused, respectful, and free of any offensive or harmful

material. This ensures the space is aligned with the ethical standards expected in a professional research environment.

- **Safe-for-Work (SFW) policies:** to foster a professional and inclusive environment, all shared content must be SFW, meaning that it is suitable for all Members regardless of location, time of day, or context. This includes maintaining appropriate language, imagery, and discussions.
- **Respect for research ethics:** as the digital co-working space serves a research and applied research community, moderation also ensures that all discussions and materials adhere to research ethics, such as respect for intellectual property, proper attribution of ideas, and the responsible handling of sensitive data or topics.

Additionally, to ensure smooth management and a positive experience within the digital co-working space, various moderation tools and processes have been implemented. One key tool is the **Maki Bot**, which has been added to the server. Maki Bot serves multiple functions, including:

- **Welcome and support moderation:** Maki Bot automates welcoming new Members and assists in moderating interactions to maintain a respectful and productive environment.
- **(Voice) levels** tracks and encourages user activity and engagement within voice channels.
- **Music:** offers features for playing music during events or breaks in voice channels.
- **Logs and invite tracking:** Maki Bot maintains records of server activities, such as messages and role changes, for transparency and review. It also monitors how Members are invited and join the community, providing insights into community growth.
- **Reaction labels:** allows members to assign roles to themselves using reaction emojis, making role/label distribution efficient and user-friendly.
- **Dashboard:** as a backstage feature, it provides an easy-to-use interface for managing all the bot's functions and customizing settings as needed.

This combination of features ensures that the community operates smoothly, remains organized, and encourages active engagement, while maintaining a welcoming and respectful atmosphere.

Moreover, other Bots could be added in the platform, to facilitate the access and use of the different functions during IMPULSE implementation. Especially after the Pre-Hackathons and the Final Hackathon the Discord channel will be updated to achieve iterative improvements in the digital experiences of the IMCo Members.

8 Annex

8.1 Joining IMCo: a step-by-step guide

Upon receiving the invitation link and clicking on it (<https://discord.gg/UfEggM8B>), a screen similar to the one displayed in Figure 5.1 will appear in your browser (both PC and mobile). Click the "**Accept Invite**" button to **enter** the **IMPULSE | Community of Practice of Practice** Discord server.

Figure 5.1. Screenshot displaying the gateway to joining the IMPULSE digital co-working space.

If you don't have a Discord account, after clicking "**Accept Invite**", you are prompted to a slightly different screen (Figure 5.2). Here, you will be asked to:

- **Enter your display name:** You are asked to choose a name that will be visible to other members of the community. You can use letters, special characters, or emojis to personalize your display name.
- **Agree to terms:** before proceeding, you need to check the box indicating that you have read and agree to Discord's **Terms of Service** and **Privacy Policy**.
- **Click on "Continue":** after filling in your name and agreeing to the terms, click "**Continue**" to finalise your registration and enter the server.

Figure 5.2. Screenshot displaying the gateway to the Discord server if no Discord account has been created.

Then, you will be asked to input your **Birth Date** (Figure 5.3) and your **email-address** (Figure 5.4) to automatically complete the registration of your account on Discord.

Figure 5.3. Insert your birth date.

Figure 5.4. Insert your email address to complete registration on Discord.

Done!

8.2 A quick onboarding

Once you are in, you will be guided through the server by a quick onboarding process designed to help new Members familiarize themselves with the **IMPULSE | Community of Practice** server and its structure. Here is a breakdown of the steps:

1. Introduction and interest (channel priority) selection:

- The first prompt asks if the user would like to know more about IMPULSE. Members can select either "Yes" to learn more or "I already know IMPULSE" to skip the details.
- The second prompt allows the user to select specific areas of interest from the **IMPULSE prototypes**—Education, Creation, and Connection. This helps Members direct their focus and participate in discussions most relevant to their expertise or interests.

Figure 5.5. Step 1 of the onboarding process “Introduction and interest (channel priority) selection”

- **Onboarding checklist** (Figure 5.6): After selecting their interests, users are introduced to the server layout. A welcome message from a server moderator provides an overview of what the IMPULSE co-working space offers. Here, Members are given simple tasks, such as introducing themselves, exploring upcoming events, starting discussions, and reading the rules to get acquainted with the server channels and its community.

Figure 5.6. Onboarding checklist suggesting quick tasks to members to introduce themselves to the community and browse the server.

- **Inviting other members:** inviting others to a Discord server is simple and can be done by any existing participant who has the necessary permissions. To invite new members, users can generate and share invite links. Here is how:
 - **Right-click on the server icon:** on the left sidebar where all your servers are listed, right-click on the icon of the server you want to invite someone to.
 - **Select "Invite People":** from the dropdown menu, click on the "Invite People" option. This will open a window that generates an invite link.

- **Copy the invite link:** once the invite link is displayed, you can copy it by clicking the "Copy" button. You can then paste this link in a message or email to share with others.
- **Additionally,** the invite links can be customized with specific permissions, expiration dates, or a limit on the number of times it can be used, offering greater control over how new members are invited into the server.

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